

QUALITY ANALYSIS OF COASTAL WATER AT HATHAB COAST, GUJARAT, INDIA

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Abstract

Present study determines the quality of coastal water at Hathab coast located in Bhavnagar district, Gujarat, INDIA. This region comes under the area of Gulf of Cambay. Water is essential for maintaining marine ecosystem as it provide the oxygen, nutrient to the marine organism. Water quality analysis conduct by taking parameter such as Temperature, pH, Salt Concentration, Total dissolved solids (TDS), Electrical conductivity (EC), Dissolved Oxygen (DO). All these parameter taking by multi parameter testing meter. This study reviles the nature and quality of coastal water properties and gives the reference data for further environmental comparative study.

Keywords: Hathab coast, pH, EC., TDS, DO, Salt.

I. INTRODUCTION

Coastal state of Gujarat consist 1600 km long coastline with consisting 14 coastal district and 2 union territories (ipmenviis.nic.in/). Coastal area is complex and dynamic environment (Morris, et al.1995). when fresh water, high currents, rainfall, various biotic and Abiotic component mix with seawater, a various physical chemical process take place which change the water quality as well as it affect the nutrient cycle of coastal environment so, water quality direct affect the health of marine ecosystem.

A hydrological survey is important for the marine biology. Essential knowledge of the seawater quality is necessary to understand

the biology of the ocean, which is rolling in a marine environment (Harvey, 1945). Therefore, sea water quality monitoring and assessments are necessary for water quality management (Udoinyang *et al.* 2015).

Physical and chemical characteristic of water body control the distribution, development of marine flora and fauna.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Study Area

Hathab is located at Bhavnagar district in Gujarat state, India. Study site is 28 km far from Bhavnagar city and present between 21°34'02"N to 72°15'45"E.

Fig:1 study location

The shoreline is muddy to sandy and some portion having rocky area but majority portion cover by thick mud layer and sand.

Fig:2 study site

B. Method of water analysis

Marine water examined every month. The quality of marine water evaluated by determining different physic chemical parameter like Temperature, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), salt, dissolve oxygen (DO). All these parameters measure Ex-situ, using multi-parameter probe. Temperature value express in °C unit, while Electrical Conductivity (EC) express in *Millisiemens* (mS), Total Dissolved Solids(TDS) and salt value expressed as a ppt while Dissolve Oxygen (DO) vale express in mg/l unit.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

All six physicochemical parameter carried out regularly for six month (January-2021 to September -202, due to covid-19 lock down march to April data not recorded).

A. Water Temperature:

Hathab coast temperature varied from 26 °C to 34.3 °C. Temperature is one the important factor for distribution of marine flora and fauna [7]. Seawater Temperature was affected by different abiotic factor like heavy rainfall, cloudy weather, removal of shading stream bank vegetation, storm water. Maximum 34.3 °C temperature recorded in June and minimum 26 °C temperature record in January.

Graph:1 Variations in Water Temperature

B. Ph:

In natural ecosystem pH is maintained within the range of 5.5 to 8.5 [5]. The value of pH varies from 7.85 to 8.6 in study area. In month of June maximum pH value reported 8.6 and minimum pH value 7.85 reported in September month.

Graph:2 Variations in Ph

C. Electrical Conductivity (Ec):

Electrical conductivity varies from 45.1 mS to 48.3 mS. Concentration of sulphate and chloride influence the electrical conductivity of water. The fluctuation in total EC was due to fluctuation in total dissolved solids and salinity [4]. Maximum amount present in June month and minimum amount reported in January.

Graph:3 Variations in Electrical Conductivity

D. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS):

Total dissolved solids value reported in ppt unit. Total dissolved solid range from 29.9 ppt to 32.5 ppt. Maximum value is reported in month of July while minimize in month of January.

Graph:4 Variations in Total Dissolved Solids

E. Salt Concentration:

Salt concentration range from 22.6 ppt to 33ppt. salt concentration indicates the value of salinity. Salt concentration varies with temperature and different climatic factors. Maximum value reported in February month while minimum value reported in September month.

Graph:5 Variations in Salt Concentration

F. Dissolved Oxygen (Do):

Dissolved oxygen range from 3.22 mg/l to 6.5 mg/ l. in ecosystem, the relation of producer and consumers change the concentration of dissolved oxygen.

Maximum value reported in June month while minimum amount reported in July month.

Graph:6 Variation In Dissolved Oxygen

Table No. : 1 comparative table of physicochemical parameters

MONTH	TEMP (°C)	pH	EC (mS)	TDS (ppt)	SALT (ppt)	DISSOLVE OXYGEN (mg/l)
JANUARY	26	8.2	45.1	29.9	23.8	5.89
FEBRUARY	27	8.2	45.6	32	33	4.2
JUNE	34.3	8.6	48.3	31.8	24.1	6.5
JULY	30	8.32	47.1	32.5	24	3.72
AUGUST	32.3	8.3	46.6	30.8	23.4	4.8
SEPATEMBER	31.5	7.85	46.3	31.8	22.6	5.4

IV. CONCLUSION

The present study illustrates the health of coast water bodies at Hathab coast, Gujarat, India. Physicochemical analysis has achieved some important finding. The obtain result illustrate water quality according to seasonal variation. This data will be important when any pollution occurred at this site in future and that time it is used as a reference data which will help to understand the effect of climate change on marine ecosystem. Analysis reports show the pH value and dissolvedoxygen values according to the Indian standards for ecological sensitive areas for coastal waters. Salt concentration range is change due to evaporation, rainfall.

This study shows the condition of marine environment, on the basis of these study it give to chance doing further advance study like environmental correlation, Abiotic and biotic relationship, comparative analysis.

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